

Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and rhodium(III) using bis(indole-3-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone as new sensitive and selective complexing agent

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Bis(indole-3-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BIATCH) reacts with Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} forming coloured complexes (λ_{\max} 385 nm in ethyl acetate). In the presence of moderate excess of diverse ions both Pd and Rh can be determined with BIATCH. The molar extinction coefficient and Sandell's sensitivity values for both complexes have been evaluated.

In the present communication bis(indole-3-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone has been recommended as a sensitive and selective reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of both palladium and rhodium. The method is simple less time-consuming and specially sensitive for Rh in comparison of many other reagents¹. An alloy sample has also been analysed successfully with the reagent.

Results and Discussion

Both the yellow coloured complexes of Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} with BIATCH in ethyl acetate exhibit λ_{\max} at 385 nm. Both the complexes are stable for about 24 h. Maximum and constant absorbance for Pd-BIATCH complex was obtained at pH 3.0–6.5, while that for Rh-BIATCH complex at 5.3–6.5. Five different solvents were investigated as extractants for both the complexes, viz. isobutyl methyl ketone, ethyl acetate, 1,2-dichloroethane, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane and among which ethyl acetate was found most suitable for both the complexes at room temperature and constant pH. Three successive extractions with 5 ml portions of ethyl acetate revealed the degrees of extractions 98.2 and 99.2% respectively, for the Pd and Rh complexes.

The empirical formula of the complexes were determined by mole-ratio method² and verified by slope-ratio method. The composition of the Pd complex was found to be 2 : 1 (reagent : metal) and that for Rh-complex 3 : 1.

It is possible to determine 0.02 mg of Pd and 0.03 mg of Rh reliably (within $\pm 2\%$ error) in presence of the following ions (tolerance limits in mg) : for Pd^{II}, Rh^{III} respectively : Ni^{II} (5, 1), V^V (1.2, 0.8), Mo^{VI} (1, 1), Bi^{III} (0.5, 0.5), U^{VI} (2, 2) do not interfere; Pb^{II} (1, 1.5), Cr^{III} (1, 1), Mn^{II} (2, 1), Fe^{III} (2, 0.9), Co^{III} (1, 1), Cu^{II} (0.8, 1), Au^{III} (0.6, 0.3) do not interfere when masked with Mg-EDTA and EDTA only for gold; Hg^{II} (0.33, 0.3), Pt^{IV} (0.18, 0.1), Ti^{IV} (1, 1), Pd^{II} (0.14), Rh^{III} (0.31), Os^{VI} (0.06, 0.1), Ir^{III} (0.26, 0.2), Ru^{III} (0.2, 0.1) can be tolerated but interferences from Hg^{II}

is masked with KI and Ti^{IV} with NaF. In case of Rh estimation, Pd is extracted first at room temperature and at 3–4 pH then the aqueous layer is treated for Rh and estimated. Interferences of Os^{VI}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} are avoided in both cases by reduction with sulphurous acid and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively.

Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration ranges 0.89–3.1 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ for Pd and 0.48–1.99 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ for Rh at 385 nm. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for Pd and Rh complexes are respectively 2.38×10^4 and 0.0045, and $4.28 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0025 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

For the Pd complex with 24 μg of the metal, the average of six determination is $23.91 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g}$ at 95% confidence limit and that for Rh complex with 31.25 μg is $31.20 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{g}$ at 95% confidence limit.

The proposed method was applied for the determination of Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} in various synthetic mixture of platinum metals and thermocouple wire alloy sample. The results show that for 5 parallel determinations of 24.0 μg of Pd and 31.25 μg of Rh in the synthetic mixture of platinum metals, the relative mean error are 0.52 and 0.56 respectively. Whereas for binary mixture of Pd (24.0 μg) and Rh (31.25 μg), the relative mean error is 0.75 and 0.61 respectively. And the 23.35 μg of Rh in thermocouple wire sample shows the relative mean error of 0.35.

Experimental

A Hitachi 3210 spectrophotometer was used. The pH was measured with a Systronics 324 pH meter.

Palladium chloride (PdCl₂) and rhodium chloride (RhCl₃·3H₂O), (J.M.) were dissolved separately in dilute HCl and standardised³. Standard solutions by other metal ions were prepared by dissolving their salts in distilled water or in dilute HCl.

Bis(indole-3-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BIATCH) was prepared⁴ by condensation of indole-3-aldehyde⁵ (2 mol) and thiocarbohydrazide⁶ (1 mol) and recrystallised

from dimethylformamide-water mixture as yellow flaky crystals, m.p. 220°. A solution of this reagent ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) in specpure alcohol was prepared.

All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : An aliquot containing known amount of Pd^{II} was taken, its pH adjusted to 3.0–6.5 with dilute HCl and 10% Na-acetate solution. The reagent solution ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$; 1–2 cm³) was then added to it and the mixture was allowed to stand for 10–15 min at room temperature. The resulting yellow complex was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 cm³), made up to 25 ml with ethyl acetate, dried with Na₂SO₄ and its absorbance measured at 385 nm against the reagent blank. In case of rhodium the pH was adjusted to 5.3–6.5 with the prepared buffer solution. After addition of reagent solution (1–2 cm³) the mixture was heated over a boiling-water-bath for 30–35 min and then cooled to room temperature. Subsequent extraction and absorbance measurements at 385 nm were the same as for palladium.

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